

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF KNITTED FABRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The tensile properties of carbon fibre knitted fabric reinforced epoxy composite laminates have been improved in two ways. Firstly, by increasing the tow size of spun yarn in the knit. Secondly, by insertion of additional straight carbon fibres between the face and back loops of 1X1 rib fabric. The elastic and strength properties in tension were measured in the warp and weft directions and the influence of the inlaid fibres evaluated. Failure mechanisms associated with different fibre arrangements were identified.

Key words: Knitted fabrics; Mechanical properties; Failure mechanisms; Carbon fibres.

1. INTRODUCTION

Knitted fabric preforms offer a new route to the mass production of composite components using resin transfer moulding. Existing textile technology can be readily adopted for producing various types of knitted fabric preforms [1]. Knitted fabric composites have higher interlaminar shear and through thickness properties. However, they have lower in-plane mechanical properties than conventional laminated composites mainly because the volume fraction of fibres (V_f) is smaller and the fibres are arranged in a three dimensional array. Rudd et al., reported [2] that glass fibre knitted fabric composites gave lower mechanical properties than random glass fibre composites. Using a cross floating technique they improved the laminate stiffness but the strength values remained low. In the present work an attempt has been made to improve the mechanical properties by modifying the knitted fabric both by increasing the tow size of spun yarn in the knit and by the insertion of straight fibres.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Spun carbon fibre yarns (Heltra-GrafitexTM) were weft knitted by Courtaulds, U.K, on a seven gauge flat bed knitting machine with a simple 1X1 rib structure (figure 1a). A series of fabrics were produced with different tow sizes of spun yarn i.e. 1.3K, 2.6K and 3.9K (K indicates 1000 filaments). Another set of fabrics with 6K and 12K tows of continuous carbon fibres (Grafil-EXAS) inserted between the face and back loops of 2.6K knit in the weft direction (figure 1b) were produced. Resin transfer moulding and Ciba-Giegy cold setting epoxy resin were used to fabricate flat composite laminates with different volume fractions of fibres ranging from 10 to 35%. Two layers of each fabric, without and with inlay fibres were used to fabricate laminates of 3 mm and 4 mm thickness respectively. Immediately before injection 50 parts by volume of LY1927 resin was mixed thoroughly with 40 parts by volume of hardener HY1927. After injection the composite was held for 16 hours at room temperature prior to extraction from the mould. The laminates were further cured at 60°C for two hours and at 80°C for two hours in an air circulating furnace. A post curing treatment at 100°C for 24 hours was given to obtain optimum mechanical properties. The volume fraction of fibres was determined using the acid digestion method. Tensile specimens of 200 mm long and 30 mm wide were cut parallel to the warp and weft directions. Glass epoxy end tabs were glued to prevent the specimen failure in the grips. Tensile tests were conducted using a 100 kN Schenck screw driven machine at a slow speed of 0.1 mm/min to follow the failure process. A minimum of three samples were tested for each fibre arrangement. Fracture surfaces were examined by stereo optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

FIGURE 1. Weft knitted 1X1 rib structure a) without inlay fibres and b) with inlay fibres.

3. TENSILE PROPERTIES

3.1 Laminates without inlay fibres: The tensile strength and modulus parallel to the warp and weft directions of the knitted fabric are given in table 1. V_f is increased with increase of spun yarn tow size used in the knit. The properties are dependent on V_f and the direction of testing.

TABLE 1. Tensile properties of laminates without inlay fibres.

Spun yarn tow size	Volume fraction of fibres (V_f) (%)	Warp		Weft	
		Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)
1.3K	10.5	10.0±0.5	56.5±2.5	8.5±0.5	34.1±2.0
2.6K	21.0	15.0±0.5	70.3±1.5	11.8±0.5	40.9±2.0
3.9K	31.5	20.1±1.0	91.0±2.5	13.5±0.5	42.5±1.0

FIGURE 2. Stress-strain curves for warp tested laminates with different tow sizes of spun yarn a) 1.3K, b) 2.6K and c) 3.9K.

3.1.1 Warp direction: Both tensile strength and modulus increased with increase of spun yarn tow size. This is attributed to the increased volume fraction of fibres. Typical stress-strain curves are shown in figure 2. The curves are linear up to a certain stress level or knee point. The slope of the linear portion was used to determine the modulus. The strain at the knee point was about 0.3% and was almost independent of yarn tow size. However, the stress corresponding to the knee point increased with the yarn tow size from 30 MPa for the 1.3K yarn to 62 MPa for 3.9K yarn. The non-linearity of the curves above the knee point was related to the onset of various micro failure mechanisms. The stress-strain curve of the 3.9K yarn composite

laminates was more serrated than for the other laminates. These serrations are related to crack nucleation and growth mechanisms operating in the composite.

3.1.2 Weft direction: The weft properties were lower than the warp properties (table 1). This may be attributed to greater length of fibre aligned in the warp direction compared to weft direction in 1X1 rib fabric. Typical stress-strain curves are shown in figure 3. The tensile modulus increased with the tow size of spun yarn, whereas the tensile strength showed only a relatively small increase. In contrast to specimens tested in the warp direction, the stress-strain curves showed a large drop in the stress prior to complete fracture. This was followed by a small build up of stress before final separation of the fracture surfaces. The large stress drop was associated with the formation of transverse cracks across the width of the specimen. These cracks propagated through the specimen thickness and coalesced, resulting in complete separation of fracture surfaces, except for bridging of fibres.

FIGURE 3. Stress-strain curves for weft tested laminates with different tow sizes of spun yarn a) 1.3K, b) 2.6K and c) 3.9K.

3.2 Laminates with inlay fibres: The effect of inlay fibres on the tensile properties of laminates with 2.6K spun yarn are summarised in the table 2.

TABLE 2. Tensile properties of laminates with inlay fibres.

Inlay fibre tow size	Volume fraction of fibres (V_f) (%)	Warp		Weft	
		Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)
0K	21.0	15.0±0.5	70.3±1.5	11.8±0.5	40.9±2.0
6K	20.4	14.0±0.5	59.0±1.0	16.8±1.0	152.5±6.5
12K	24.4	15.0±0.5	63.0±1.0	34.5±1.0	220.4±5.0

3.2.1 Warp direction: The presence of inlay fibres had no effect on the tensile modulus and produced a small decrease in the tensile strength. Typical stress-strain curves for laminates with

6K and 12K inlay fibres are shown in figure 4. The curves were more serrated than those for similar laminates without inlay fibres (figure 2). The knee point occurred at a significantly lower stress of 30 MPa compared to 40 MPa for the laminate without inlay fibres.

FIGURE 4. Stress-strain curves for laminates tested in warp direction a) 6K inlay fibres and b) 12K inlay fibres and weft direction c) 6K inlay fibres and d) 12K inlay fibres.

3.2.2 Weft direction: The tensile strength and modulus increased with increase of the inlay fibres and were significantly higher than for the material without inlay fibres. Typical stress-strain curves for laminates with 6K and 12K inlay fibres are shown in the figure 4. The curves were linear up to a stress level as high as 100 MPa, compared with 25 MPa for composites without inlay fibres (figure 3b). The curves were smooth up to ultimate failure without any large drops in stress.

4. OPTICAL AND SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

The appearance of the fracture surfaces was dependent on tow size, fibre arrangement and direction of applied tensile stress. The details are far too complicated to be described in this brief paper, but three main features were identified on all the fractured specimens which are directly relevant to the failure behaviour of these materials. These may be summarised as follows:

a) Fibre bundle debonding: The overall path of fracture was normal to the applied stress and followed an approximately planar array of fibre bundle loops as illustrated schematically in figure 5 for knitted reinforcement without inlay fibres.

FIGURE 5. Schematic diagram of stretched 1X1 rib fabric illustrating the fracture path of a) warp tested laminate and b) weft tested laminate. Dotted lines indicate the back loops and the solid lines indicate the face loops of the fabric. Thick lines shows the debonding of fibre bundles.

A side view of the fracture path is shown in figure 6 for a laminate with a single knitted layer viewed in transmitted light. The dark lines are the fibre bundles and the windows between the bundles are resin rich areas, which are relatively large in this low V_f material. The fine lines in the windows are individual fibres resulting from the 'hairiness' of the spun yarn fibre bundles.

The fracture path follows the convex surface of the curved fibre bundles where they are aligned perpendicular to the tensile stress. Figure 7 shows the typical imprints of fibre bundles on a fracture surface. On opposite fracture surface the fibres were exposed indicating that crack propagation occurred at the fibre matrix interface of the fibres on the out side of the bundle.

b) Resin matrix cracking: Fracture of the resin was initiated at the fibre bundles. This was illustrated in figure 8. The river line markings spread out radially from the edge of the fibre bundle. This effect was particularly marked in the laminates reinforced with knits containing inlay fibres tested in the warp direction, i.e. normal to the inlay fibre direction (figure 9). Failure at the surface of the bundles of inlay fibres led to resin fracture, as revealed by the river line patterns.

c) Fibre bundle fracture: Fracture of the fibre bundles occurred in the same plane as the main fracture path with very little pull-out of the bundles (figure 7). As will be evident from figure 5 the fracture plane is close to the interlocking points in the knit and in these positions the fractured bundles are approximately parallel to the tensile stress. The overall path of fracture was similar in laminates with inlay fibres. Tensile testing parallel to the inlay fibres resulted in fracture of the inlay fibres with some pull-out (figure 10).

5. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that the tensile properties of knitted fabric reinforced composites increased with volume fraction of fibres and was dependent on the direction of testing. The properties were superior in the warp direction compared to the weft direction. Significant increases in modulus and tensile strength were achieved by inserting unidirectional tows of carbon fibres in the weft direction.

The stress-strain curves illustrated in figures 2 and 4 show that fracture was preceded by non-linear deformation which was sometimes associated with a serrated stress-strain response. In the absence of serrations the non-linearity may be attributed to resin deformation although some microfracture may have occurred. This is currently being investigated using acoustic emission. The serrations were caused by microcracking, which was particularly pronounced in tests parallel to the warp direction of the laminates with inlay fibres (figures 4 a and 4b). In these tests it was observed that microcracks normal to the tensile stress, found along the whole gauge length prior to fracture.

The sequence of events leading to the fracture have been identified from observations of the fracture surfaces. The cracks nucleated at the surface of the bundle at portions of the knitted array where the bundle was normal to the tensile stress. The strain at crack initiation was between 0.2 and 1.0% depending on the fibre architecture. These strains corresponds closely to those expected for failure of unidirectional material tested in tension transverse to the fibre direction [3]. The cracks propagated in a brittle manner through the adjacent resin rich regions. So that the applied loads are redistributed to the fibre bundles aligned in the tensile stress direction, which then fail. The absence of fibre bundle pull-out at the portions of the bundle

fractures in the fracture plane is a direct result of the sharp radii of curvature in the yarn of the knitted fabrics, particularly at the interlocking points.

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FIGURE 6. Optical photograph showing the side view of the weft tested monolayer composite with 1.3K spun fibres. Shows a) debonded fibre bundles and knit pattern, b) windows indicate the resin rich areas and c) fine lines indicate the 'hairiness' of spun yarn. Magnification 12X.

FIGURE 7. SEM fractograph of warp tested double layer composite laminate with 3.9K spun yarn. Shows a) imprints of the fibre bundles b) matrix river lines and c) fractured fibre bundles.

FIGURE 8. SEM fractograph of warp tested double layer composite laminate with 1.3K spun yarn. Shows matrix river lines spreading out from the debonded fibre bundle.

FIGURE 9. SEM fractograph of warp tested double layer composite laminate with 12K inlay fibres. Shows a) delaminated inlay fibres b) matrix river lines and c) fractured fibre bundle.

FIGURE 10. SEM fractograph of weft tested double layer composite laminate with 12K inlay fibres. Shows a) small pull-out of fractured inlay fibres, b) hole left by the fractured inlay fibres, c) debonded fibre bundles and d) matrix river lines.